

Human thermal modeling with voxelized body domains

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Introduction

The interaction of the human body with the environment is a complex phenomenon. Most full body thermal models use finite element or finite difference methods to represent and solve the complicated domain structure. With finite element approaches, challenges in mesh handling and programming for complicated equations are often encountered. Alternatively, finite difference methods are useful when boundaries separating two regions are well-characterized in equation form. These methods are difficult to apply to the human body, where surface equations are often very complicated or unknown. Another very important consideration is that computed tomography data are inherently voxelized. For example information received from a CT scan is pixelized. A voxelized domain such as this is easily adapted to the finite volume method and being an integral approach provides addition flexibility in complicated domains. The geometric characteristics of an array of rectangular prisms is interesting to consider. Shrinking the dimension of the rectangular prism allows a voxelized domain to converge on volume as shown in Figure 1. But also as important, the geometry of the rectangle prevents surface area convergence. The purpose of the current paper is to document how this surface area error effects application of the bio-heat equation to human body models that could be constructed from data such as those obtained from detailed CT scans.

Figure 1: Cuboidal Pixel Representation of a circle; (a) Coarser Mesh; (b) Coarser mesh and Finer Mesh

Methods

The Pennes Bio heat equation developed by Pennes [1] is often used to mathematically model the heat transfer in the body [2,3] and is used for the current study. If at steady state, the modes of heat transfer are conduction, convection and blood perfusion as shown:

$$\nabla^2(kT) + \dot{q}_m + \omega\rho_b c_b(T_a - T) = 0.$$

Where, k is the Thermal Conductivity, $W/m^{\circ}C$, \dot{q}_m Heat generation rate, W/m^3 , ω blood perfusion, T_a temperature of arterial, density of blood and specific heat of the blood. Using the finite volume formulation, the following voxel heat transfer equations can be obtained after some manipulation. This approach uses the psudo overall heat transfer coefficient (U) to model energy transfer between the volumes. Figure 2 shows the nodal layout for the equations shown on the left.

$$\frac{1}{U_{left}} = \frac{dx}{2k_{i-1,j}} + \frac{dx}{2k_{i,j}}$$

$$\frac{1}{U_{right}} = \frac{dx}{2k_{i,j}} + \frac{dx}{2k_{i+1,j}}$$

$$\frac{1}{U_{bottom}} = \frac{dy}{2k_{i,j}} + \frac{dy}{2k_{i,j-1}}$$

$$\frac{1}{U_{top}} = \frac{dy}{2k_{i,j}} + \frac{dy}{2k_{i,j+1}}$$

Figure 2: Cubic Voxel Domain

Problem Statement

The effect of surface was demonstrated on a simplified geometry that is representative of a human arm. The arm has a radius 3cm, thermal conductivity $0.3 W/m^{\circ}C$, convection heat transfer coefficient for air as $3.1 W/m^2^{\circ}C$ at the outside and a metabolic heat generation rate as $1333W/m^3$. A theoretical solution to this

problem can be obtained allowing a direct comparison with the voxelized domain solution shown above. The domain is discretized to a size of 1mm x 1mm, 2mmx2mm, and 3mmx3mm. The ambient temperature has been set to 20°C.

Figure 3. shows the surface temperature for the four cubic voxels and the theoretical solution. Regardless of the dimensions the local surface temperature is about 1.5 C below the theoretical solution. The finer the mesh the less the variation in temperature around the skin surface.

Figure 3: Cubic Voxel body Surface Temperature

The results show, the voxels have an inherent drawback due to their geometry. The surface temperature shows an error of 1.5°C. This error is independent of mesh size for finer meshes and would exist as long as voxels are used as the shape of the mesh elements.

Conclusions

Cubic voxels hold potential for human thermal modeling as it can rapidly be adapted a FVM method. Volume is shown to converge for smaller sized voxels but surface area does not. This limits the accuracy of the approach. A new method is proposed to overcome this error by triangulizing the voxels

References

- [1] Pennes, Harry H. "Analysis of tissue and arterial blood temperatures in the resting human forearm." *Journal of applied physiology* 1, no. 2 (1948): 93-122.
- [2] Fiala, Dusan, Kevin J. Lomas, and Martin Stohrer. "A computer model of human thermoregulation for a wide range of environmental conditions: the passive system." *Journal of applied physiology* 87, no. 5 (1999): 1957-1972.
- [3] Sun, Xiaoyang, Steve Eckels, and Zhongquan Charlie Zheng. "An improved thermal model of the human body." *HVAC&R Research* 18, no. 3 (2012): 323-338.